

Alkali Metal Complexes : Mixed Ligand Complexes of Alkali-Metal Salts of Anthranilic Acid, Phenylanthranilic Acid, *o*-Aminophenol and *o*-Nitrobenzoic Acid with Some Oxygen and Nitrogen Donor Ligands.

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Mixed ligand complexes of the alkali metal salts of the title compounds with 8-hydroxyquinoline, 1-nitroso-2-naphthol, isonitrosoacetophenone have been synthesised. These complexes have been found to be less stable than the corresponding aliphatic aminoacid complexes. The number of second ligand in the adducts appeared to be favoured by increase in the radius or possibly decrease in the ionisation potential of the alkali metal. Strong to medium hydrogen bonding is one of the stabilising factors of these complexes in the solid state. Preliminary chelation by the metal salts is an essential feature for adduct formation and the second ligand should also be a potential chelate.

THE preferential intake of alkali metals by animals may have some co-relation with amino acid complexes of alkali metals. For a comparative and fuller study of the coordinating ability of the alkali metal salts of amino acids, further syntheses of the complexes of alkali metal anthranilates, phenylanthranilates, *o*-aminophenolates and *o*-nitrobenzoates with same oxygen and nitrogen donor ligands have been made.

Results

The method of preparation of these mixed complexes were similar to the ones reported in previous papers.

The physical properties are similar to those of alkali metal glycinate and β -alaninate complexes described previously. Analytical results and selected i. r. bands are given in Tables 1 and 2.

TABLE I

Compound	Colour	Transition temp. or decomposition temp. (°C)	Calcd.				Found			
			C	H	N	M	C	H	N	M
LiAnc.8HQ	Dirty white	208 t	66.00	4.51	9.76		66.05	4.47	10.05	
NaAnc.8HQ	Dirty white	130 t	63.26	4.27	9.21	7.56	63.07	4.25	8.75	7.48
K Anc.8HQ	Dirty white	177 d	60.00	4.06	8.75	12.18	60.14	4.14	7.65	11.98
RbAnc.8HQ	Dirty white	128 t	52.30	3.81	7.65	23.22	52.13	3.84	7.60	22.62
NaAnc.1N2N	Brown	191 t	60.14	3.90	8.43	6.95	59.81	3.79	8.40	6.80
K Anc.1N2N	Mustard	185 t	58.62	3.80	8.04	11.20	58.30	3.80	7.95	11.00
RbAnc.1N2N	Brown	110 t	51.60	3.30	7.10	21.57	50.78	3.12	6.98	21.12
CsAnc.1N2N	Mustard	303-305 t	46.25	2.94	6.34	29.70	46.34	2.86	6.30	29.00
CsAnc.1NAP	Pale yellow	125 t	43.26	2.88	6.71	31.43	43.24	2.52	6.68	30.95
LiphAnc.8HQ	White	200-02 t	72.52	4.67	7.69		72.40	4.50	7.55	
NaphAnc.8HQ	White	175 t	69.47	4.47	7.36	6.05	69.20	4.45	7.40	5.96
NaphAnc.1N2N	Reddish brown	150 t	67.64	4.15	6.86	5.63	67.75	4.12	6.90	5.85
KphAnc.1N2N	Brownish green	155-60 t	65.09	4.00	6.60	9.19	64.90	3.95	6.65	9.05
RbphAnc.1N2N	Brownish black	120 t	58.72	3.61	5.95	18.08	58.42	3.68	6.00	17.75
CsphAnc.1N2N	Brownish green	115 t	53.28	3.28	5.40	25.67	52.98	3.20	5.45	24.78
LiOAP.8HQ	Light brown	202 d	69.23	5.00	10.76		69.20	5.15	10.66	
NaOAP.8HQ	Light brown	186 d	65.21	4.71	10.10	8.33	64.95	4.82	10.00	8.34
K OAP.8HQ	Light brown	165 t	61.64	4.45	9.58	13.35	61.44	4.86	9.55	13.10
CsOAP.8HQ	Brown	120 t	46.75	3.37	7.25	34.28	46.80	3.62	7.20	34.15
LiONBA.8HQ	White	153 t	60.37	3.45	8.80		59.80	3.50	8.75	
NaONBA.8HQ	Light brown	145 t	57.48	3.29	8.38	6.88	57.24	3.20	8.35	6.75
NaONBA.1N2N	Yellowish green	170 t	56.35	3.03	7.73	6.35	56.28	3.00	7.70	6.25
K ONBA.1N2N	Brownish green	153 t	53.96	2.91	7.40	10.31	53.40	2.95	7.35	9.98
NaONBA. ONP	Orange	95 t	47.56	2.74	8.54	7.01	47.75	2.68	8.50	6.80

Anc=Anthranilic acid ; 8HQ=8-hydroxyquinoline ; 1N2N=1-nitroso-2-naphthol ; INAP=isonitrosoacetophenone ; phAnc=phenylanthranilic acid ; OAP=*o*-aminophenol ; ONBA=*o*-nitrobenzoic acid ; & ONP=*o*-nitrophenol.

TABLE 2—SELECTED ABSORPTION BANDS IN DIFFERENT REGIONS (cm⁻¹).

Compound	3500 — 3000	2700 — 1800	1700 — 1500			
Anthranilic acid (Anc)	3410 3270		1660			
8-Hydroxyquinoline (8HQ)	3440				1580	
LiAnc	3380 3270		1660	1615	1590	1520
LiAnc.8HQ	3340br 3240br	2200br	1660	1610	1580	1500
NaAnc.8HQ		1800br				
KAnc.	3420 3320		1680sh	1605	1580	1515
KAnc.8HQ	3440 3320	1910	1660sh	1610	1580,	1570
RbAnc	3420 3280		1650	1605	1575	1505
RbAnc.8HQ	3420 3310		1650	1610	1560	1520
1-Nitroso-2-naphthol (1N2N)						
NaAnc.1N2N	3300br 3055		1640 (N=O)			
K Anc.1N2N	3420 3320	1910br	1645	1605	1570	1540
RbAnc.1N2N		2200br				1530
Isonitrosoacetophenone (INAP)						
CsAnc.INAP	3415 3300	1900br	1680	1655	1590	1564
LiphAnc.8HQ		2600	1660sh	1655	1610	1575
NaphAnc.8HQ		2620	1900			1510
NaphAnc.1N2N		2650	2360br			
KphAnc.1N2N	3200br		1900br	1650 (N=O)		
RbphAnc.1N2N		2710	2220br	1620		
CsphAnc.1N2N		2710		1630		
o-Aminophenol (OAP)						
LiOAP.8HQ	3370 3300				1590	
NaOAP.8HQ	3420br		2200br	1620	1600	1550
KOAP.8HQ	3420br		2200br	1620	1600br	1580
CsOAP.8HQ	3420w		1900	1620	1570	1545
					1580sh	1505
					1570	
					1580	1500
					1560	
o-Nitrobenzoic acid (ONBA)		3200br				
LiONBA.8HQ			2200br		1600	1580
NaONBA.8HQ			1900br	1640	1610sh	1580
NaONBA.8HQ			1800br		1600	1580
K ONBA.1N2N			1840br	1640	1600	1570
NaONBA.ONP	3420		2200	1660sh	1610	1590
					1590	1550
					1580	1510

Infrared spectra

It is well known¹ that aminocarboxylic acids act as negatively charged chelating ligands towards metal ions, coordinating both through the -NH₂ and the -COO⁻ groups. The ligand, anthranilic acid has three medium, well resolved absorption bands between 3410 and 3270 cm⁻¹. For this reason a well defined trend in the ν(NH₂) frequencies is not observable for their transition metal complexes, although there is a general lowering of the absorption range. Similar shift of the absorption range of N-H has been observed in the alkali metal anthranilates which might be due to coordination of -NH₂ group to the alkali metal.

The spectra of the mixed ligand complexes differ from the spectra of metal anthranilates and the second ligands (8HQ, 1N2N, & INAP) by the absence of the O-H stretching frequency band above 3000 cm⁻¹; instead a new broad band of medium intensity appear between 2200-1800 cm⁻¹. These bands could be assigned to the O...H...O absorption which would account for the absence of O-H absorption above 3000 cm⁻¹.

The 1700-1500 cm⁻¹ bands though metal sensitive, have not been studied in detail and not assigned to any particular frequency.

The most important difference in phenylanthranilate complexes, however, was that the hydroxy stretching frequency characteristic of 8 hydroxyquinoline and 1-nitroso-2-naphthol in Nujol mulls were found in the physical mixture (1:1 = alkali-metal salt : ligand) but not in the adducts, while the latter showed a broad absorption in the ranges 2360-1800 cm⁻¹.

Broad band in the 2300-1800 cm⁻¹ region have been attributed to the O.. H O stretching frequency in the hydrogen bonded system.

The weak broad band centered around 2600 cm⁻¹ may be due to NH⁺ O (discussed earlier).

The only few isolable o-aminophenolate and o-nitrobenzoate complexes also show medium to strong hydrogen bonding in the 2600-1800 cm⁻¹ region.

The 1700-1500 cm^{-1} bands though metal sensitive, have not been studied in detail and not assigned to any particular frequency.

Discussion

From the study of the complexes of alkali metal salts of the amino acids (e. g., anthranilic acid, phenylanthranilic acid, glycine, β -alanine), *o*-aminophenol and *o*-nitrobenzoic acid with various oxygen and nitrogen donor ligands, such as 8-hydroxyquinoline, isonitrosoacetophenone, 1-nitroso-2-naphthol, *o*-nitrophenol and acetylacetone, it has been observed that largest number of complexes with almost all the second ligands and all the members of the alkali metals (Li-Cs) were isolated in solid state with alkali metal salts of glycine and β -alanine.

The alkali metal salts of anthranilic acid, which has one amino and the carboxyl group attached to the phenyl ring, also formed relatively smaller number of complexes with 8-hydroxyquinoline and 1-nitroso-2-naphthol, but with isonitrosoacetophenone only one compound with caesium anthranilate was obtained. It is found that the substitution of one proton of the amino group of anthranilic acid by a phenyl group reduces its binding ability, as the phenylanthranilic acid formed comparatively a lesser number of complexes. Its alkali metal salts formed no compounds with isonitrosoacetophenone and only lithium and sodium salts formed complexes with 8-hydroxyquinoline.

The alkali metal salts of *o*-nitrobenzoic acid, in which the $-\text{NH}_2$ group of an anthranilic acid is completely replaced by a nitro group does not form any complex with the higher members of the alkali metal group.

The coordinating ability of *o*-aminophenol, which has a phenolic group instead of an acidic carboxyl group is further reduced, as its alkali metal salts formed no complexes with *o*-nitrophenol, 1-nitroso-2-naphthol, isonitrosoacetophenone and acetylacetone but these replace *o*-aminophenol from its metal salts. The alkali metal salts of *o*-aminophenol form compounds only with 8-hydroxyquinoline.

From the comparative study of alkali metal salts of anthranilic acid, phenylanthranilic acid, *o*-aminophenol and *o*-nitrobenzoic acid with oxygen and nitrogen donor ligands we observe that in these mixed ligand complexes of the general formula $\text{ML}_n\text{HL}'$, n is always one. With glycine and β -alanine alkali metal salt adducts, the value of n is only one for lithium and sodium, whereas in potassium, rubidium and caesium adducts, the number of second ligand is more than one; in K it is usually two, whereas Rb and Cs prefer three, but one or two are not uncommon.

Evidence² has been presented for rare earth EDTA complexes in which the assumption of a coordination number of seven or eight seems to explain the experimental observation more satisfactorily than a coordina-

tion number of six. The open chain aliphatic amino acid salts develop the property of attracting O-, N-, ligand chelates and hold them more firmly than the closed chain ones. Or in other words we can say that the metal ions in these open chain acids develop some covalent character and are more prone to the attack of chelates and thereby attain greater stability by increasing the coordination number from 2 to 4 and 6. The β -alanine complexes are easier to synthesise than the glycine complexes and increase from 5- to 6-membered ring in the system may decrease the solubility of the complex in the particular solvent.

The flat structure of glycine and β -alanine, chelated to the alkali metal through $-\text{NH}_2$ and COOH^- group, together with the larger size of the alkali metals should allow sufficient room for the second (or more) molecule to become attached to the 1:1 metal salt species, and the formation (and isolation) should be influenced predominantly by the increasing affinity of the alkali metal ion for complex formation, as the atomic number increases. A point should be reached, however, at which the increasing steric factor due to shrinkage of the available space in which to add the second ligand (or ligands) should counter balance the increasing complex forming tendency. Beyond this the steric hindrance should be the predominant factor in determining the stability (and isolation) of the complex.

The high transition temperatures of the several 1 : 3 complexes of Rb and Cs suggest a coordination number larger than six. However, in absence of definitive structure studies, it is, of course, impossible to make an absolute prediction. The number of second ligand in the adducts appeared to be favoured by increase in the radius or possible decrease in the ionisation potential of the alkali metal.

The second ligands which had lower pK values than glycine and β -alanine, also formed adduct with glycine and β -alanine salts and do not replace the glycine and β -alanine from their metal salts.

This suggests that pK is not the only dominant factor in the formation of these alkali metal adducts. One of the other factors may be the chelating ability of the ligand towards the metal ion, as has been experienced in case of mixed ligand complexes of transition metals.

One feature of these adducts is that the anion L (the first ligand) and L' (the second ligand) must be capable of chelation to form 5 or 6-membered ring. Although acetic acid and *m*-nitrophenol have a high pK (=8.18), which favours adduct formation, no adduct was formed either by an alkali metal salts of acetic acid (L) with organic acids (L'=potential O- or N- atom chelates) or with glycinate (L=potential O- or N- atom chelate) and *m*-nitrophenol (L').

These implies that not only preliminary chelation by the metal is essential for adduct formation, but the second ligand should be a potential chelate.

